

GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT THE CONCEPT OF SYNTAX

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Abstract:

Syntax is the study of how words and morphemes combine to form larger units such as phrases and sentences. Central concerns of syntax include word order, grammatical relations, hierarchical sentence structure (constituency), agreement, the nature of crosslinguistic variation, and the relationship between form and meaning (semantics). There are numerous approaches to syntax that differ in their central assumptions and goals. This article describes about the concept of syntax.

Key words: concept, syntax, equal connection, subordinate connection.

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Syntax is derived from the Greek word "Syntax" which means "composition". Syntax is a branch of grammar that studies the relationship between words and sentences, the types of word combinations and sentences, and the methods of combining them. In this respect, syntax differs from morphology. Because morphology examines the structure, formation, type, and pronunciation of words. Syntax studies the dynamics of these forms, their function and role in expressing a certain idea.

Morphology and syntax are complementary and interrelated fields. Different types of sentences - indicative, interrogative, command, exclamatory - mainly depend on the type of words used to express the clauses.

For example:

1. Nasir heard this tale from his grandmother. - affirmative.
2. Who did not participate in the excursion? - Interrogative sentence.

It is known that people exchange ideas and communicate with each other. And this is realized through speech. The sentence, in turn, is formed on the basis of various syntactic relationships of words. It is the main task of syntax is to learn sentences and word combinations that are a means of exchanging ideas.

Accordingly, the field of study of syntax is divided into several types.

Word-form syntax studies independent words, that is, parts of sentences, that take part in a certain form in each sentence. The syntax of the word combination studies the syntactically related units that express the concept. For example: the order of the rector, the taft of the sun, the opinion of people, the student's book. The syntax of the sentence studies syntactically interconnected, thought-expressing units - simple and compound sentences. For example: Spring has come (simple sentence). Spring has come, flowers have opened (conjunction).

Text syntax studies high-level communicative units that form a meaningful whole. The main units of syntax are:

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1. A word (lexeme) is a lexicon, a word is a form-grammatical unit. A word of a certain grammatical form (word form) performs a certain syntactic function in a sentence, is a syntactic unit and acts as a part of a sentence;

2. Syntax - words are syntactically connected to each other and form a single phrase expressing a concept. It is a vowel-forming element in a sentence.

3. Sentences are syntactically connected to form a message-expressing unit.

A word combination is a combination of two or more independent words that are semantically and grammatically connected to express the relationship between concepts. A word combination is formed by the grammatical connection of at least two independent words. A word combination is a free combination and is different from a fixed combination. The words in stative conjunctions are not interchangeable and act as part of a sentence. The words in a free compound can be interchanged, and each word in the compound can be a separate sentence. A word combination occurs as a unit of speech and in the process of speech; and a fixed combination is a language unit.

Types and features of tools representing syntactic relationships:

1) Word form. Shows the connection of one word to another word, indicates the grammatical meaning. This is considered a formal-grammatical tool, it occurs through additions:

- a) adverbs of agreement
- b) possessive suffixes,
- c) demonstrative form-number suffixes

2. Auxiliary words. In conjunctions, it performs a similar function, connects a noun to a verb, and is considered a lexical-grammatical tool:

- a) assistants
- b) connectives connect united clauses and sentences:

3. Word order: When expressing the syntactic function of a word with special indicators, the order plays the main role;

4. Tone. A change of stop changes the binding of the compound. Words communicate with each other in two ways:

- a) equal connection;
- b) subordinate connection.

In an equal conjunction, the words are the same part of the sentence and are joined by counting tone or conjunctions. They are equal to the participle and act as part of the same sentence. With the replacement of such fragments, the meaning and grammatical status does not change. In the subordinate connection, one of the main and one of the subordinate words come into contact. One of them complements and explains the other. Therefore, the word that defines and fills in is subordinate, and the word that is connected with it is the dominant word and performs different syntactic functions in the sentence. Accordingly, the types of dependence are as follows: Adaptation. The main feature of such subordination is that one part of subordination serves to determine another. The subordinate word and the dominant word match each other, the action, sign and object are shown to which subject they belong. Management. In this connection, the subordinate word changes its form as required by the dominant word.

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